

Dice Games on Students' Academic Achievement in Concept of Probability in Bayelsa State, Nigeria.

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Abstract

This study aimed to investigate the impact of dice games on students' academic achievement in the concept of probability. The study was guided by two research questions and hypotheses. A quasi-experimental research design was adopted. The study population consisted of 2,500 senior secondary school (SS II) students from 34 secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State. A sample of 100 SS II students was selected from two schools (one intact class from each school), with 50 students (37 males and 13 females) in the experimental group and 50 in the control group. The research instrument, a Probability Achievement Test (PAT) developed by the researcher, was validated for both face and content by two experts in mathematics and one from measurement and evaluation. The reliability of the instrument was determined using a test-retest procedure and calculated with the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC), yielding a reliability coefficient of 0.75. Mean and standard deviation were used to address the research questions, while t-test was employed to test the hypotheses at a 0.05 significance level. The findings revealed a significant difference in academic performance between students taught probability using dice games and those taught without. Additionally, male and female students taught with dice games also showed significant differences. These results suggest that dice games are an effective instructional method. The study recommends that secondary school mathematics teachers incorporate mathematical games into their teaching strategies.

Keywords: Dice games, Probability, Mathematics Education, Academic achievement, Gender.

Introduction

Mathematics is a field that focuses on quantity, structure, space, and change, playing a vital role in daily human activities. It is the foundation on which the economic development and prosperity of any nation is built. Mastery of mathematics is essential for an individual's meaningful and productive life. According to Ukadike (2010), mathematics is indispensable because it is applied across various human endeavors, including science and technology. Mathematical ability is vital for the economic success of societies, as math skills are key to understanding a wide range of disciplines, including engineering, sciences, social sciences, and even the arts. Mathematical proficiency plays a crucial role in the economic development of societies, as it underpins the understanding of diverse fields such as engineering, sciences, social sciences, and even the arts. In Nigeria, mathematics is particularly significant in this era of technological progress, contributing to the realization of the nation's Vision 2030 objectives (Enu et al., 2015). According to Ngussa & Mbuti (2017), the mathematics curriculum is structured to provide students with the essential knowledge and skills needed to excel in an increasingly dynamic technological landscape.

Despite its crucial role in national development and the efforts to improve the teaching and learning of mathematics in schools, there continues to be a significant issue with poor student performance in mathematics. Research has shown consistently low levels of achievement in Nigerian secondary schools (Abakpa & Iji, 2011). Reports from the Chief Examiner for the WASSCE in 2017 and 2018 revealed that many students scored either zero or near zero in mathematics. This indicates that poor performance is not only widespread but also more pronounced in certain areas of the mathematics curriculum, such as probability, which students have found particularly challenging. To address this, there has been a shift toward using mathematical games as a strategy to enhance students' cognitive abilities and strengthen their understanding of mathematical concepts.

Educational games, as defined by Shatz (2015), are games intentionally designed for educational purposes or those that offer incidental educational value. These games are enjoyable social activities that incorporate goals, rules, and learning objectives. Mathematical games, specifically, are games where the structure and rules are grounded in mathematical concepts, and winning the game is directly tied to understanding these mathematical principles. Examples of mathematical games include puzzles, as well as games like Ludo or Monopoly, where elements such as dice rolls contribute to learning while simultaneously providing entertainment and stimulating curiosity. According to Nekang (2016), such games not only offer enjoyment and recreation but also foster mathematical thinking and ignite excitement and competition. They serve as a means of reinforcing learning for both winners and losers. The connection between games and mathematics lies in their shared reliance on rules, experiential learning, drills, and practical applications (Rutherford, 2015).

Mathematical games serve multiple purposes, including introducing new concepts prior to formal instruction, practicing skills, and reinforcing concepts after direct teaching. Asanre (2020) conducted research on the influence of mathematical game strategies on senior secondary school students' learning outcomes, assessing their effectiveness and highlighting the primary reasons for incorporating such games into the learning process. These include their ability to strongly motivate students, engage them actively, and foster positive attitudes toward learning factors that are widely recognized as essential for successful learning. According to Marcus et al. (2016), as long as game-based methods are utilized in classrooms, students' mathematical awareness and understanding are likely to improve. Mathematics may feel daunting to students who perceive it as difficult, and this can create a barrier to learning. However, incorporating games into lessons can change this perception, making students feel more relaxed and open to the subject. Game activities can also help students build on the informal mathematical knowledge they gain through play when they participate in problem-solving activities. Hodent (2014) suggests that there is a connection between the creative use of materials during games and children's cognitive development, implying that these activities can play a role in shaping their thinking and understanding of mathematical concepts.

Mathematical games and concepts appear in a variety of contexts, some of which are clearly defined while others may overlap or differ significantly. Given the intercultural variations in how mathematical games are approached, along with noticeable differences in play patterns, it has been suggested that the impact of these games may vary between males and females. Rudiger (2014) pointed out that the influence of mathematical games on the learning outcomes of males and females remains a topic of ongoing debate among advocates of game-based learning. Onoh (2015) found that males generally performed better than females in mathematics academic achievement, although females showed greater improvement when using self-made simulation-game cards.

Similarly, research by Gbodi & Laleye (2010) revealed a significant gender difference in achievement, with male students outperforming their female counterparts. However, both studies support the idea that when mathematical games are used in education, students regardless of gender become active participants and engaged observers in the learning process, enhancing their overall involvement and understanding of mathematical concepts like probability.

Probability, a key topic in secondary school mathematics, can be effectively taught through interactive activities such as rolling dice or multiple dice on a flat surface, which demonstrates the likelihood of certain events occurring (Kenneth, 2010). The connection between dice games, and the concept of probability, suggests that using such games in probability instruction could have significant benefits. It is speculated that incorporating dice-based activities into teaching probability will not only capture students' interest in mathematics (probability) but also improve their academic achievement in the subject.

Statement of the Problem

A nationwide survey conducted by the Science Teachers' Association of Nigeria (STAN) in 2021, through its mathematics and physics panel, revealed that many secondary school mathematics teachers identified several concepts and topics at the senior secondary level as difficult to teach and learn. Among these, probability was specifically noted as a challenging area for students. The workshop highlighted alarming trends, including low academic performance and high failure rates in critical examinations such as the West African Senior School Certificate Examination (WASSCE) and the National Examination Council (NECO) exams. Notably, over 45% of the questions in these exams are drawn from topics such as probability, trigonometry, quadratic equations, and circle geometry. However, a significant proportion of students avoid attempting questions on probability in both internal and external examinations. These findings have raised considerable concern within the educational community in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa State. Consequently, this study seeks to explore the impact of using dice games as a teaching strategy on students' academic achievement in mathematics in senior secondary schools.

Purpose of the study

The purpose of this study is to examine the impact of using dice games on students' academic achievement in the concept of probability. Specifically, the study aimed to:

1. Determine the difference in academic achievement between students taught probability using dice games and those taught using traditional methods.
2. Investigate the influence of dice games on the academic achievement of male and female students in the concept of probability using dice games.

Research questions

The following research questions guided this study:

1. What is the difference in academic achievement between students taught probability using dice games and those taught without using dice games?
2. What is the difference in academic achievement of male and female students in the concept of probability using dice games?

Research Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in academic achievement between students taught probability using dice games and those taught without dice games.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the academic achievement of male and female students taught probability using dice games.

Methodology

This study employed a quasi-experimental research design, as intact classes were used, preventing random assignment of subjects to treatment and control groups. Specifically, a pretest-posttest non-equivalent control group design was adopted. The population comprised 2,500 senior secondary two (SSII) students from 34 secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State, during the 2023/2024 academic session. A sample of 100 SSII students was selected through purposive random sampling from two schools. These students were assigned to an experimental group (School A) and a control group (School B), both retaining their intact class structures. The experimental group consisted of 50 students (37 males and 13 females), while the control group also comprises of 50 students. The experimental group was shared into groups of 5 and allotted 15 minutes from each period. This period was given to the students to use dice and generate numbers as stated in varieties of word problems on probability given to them. While the control group was taught using conventional method with the lesson note prepare for the group.

The data collection instrument was the Probability Achievement Test (PAT), which had two sections. Section A collected personal information, such as school name and gender, while Section B consisted of 20 multiple-choice questions with four options (A-D) based on SSII probability topics in the mathematics syllabus. These questions were adapted from past West African Examination Council (WAEC) exams. Each question had one correct answer and three distractors. PAT was validated for both face and content by two experts in mathematics and one from measurement and evaluation all in the department of science education, Federal University Otuoke. The reliability of the PAT was assessed using the test-retest method. It was administered to 20 students from Yenagoa Local Government Area, who were not part of the study sample. After a two-week interval, the test was re-administered, and the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) was used to determine the reliability index, which was found to be 0.75. This indicates a good level of reliability for the instrument. The study lasted for a period of five weeks with the following procedures.

Week 1: Briefing the mathematics teacher for experimental group on the effective use of dice games in teaching concept of probability and a brief orientation to the students on what game-based learning is all about. While for the control group, conventional method was used.

Week 2: Administration of pre-test to both experimental and control groups

Week 3 & 4: Introduction to the use of dice games in teaching concept of probability in mathematics. While lesson plan for conventional teaching of concept of probability was used to guide the presentation of the lesson for the control group.

Week 5: Revision and post-test administration.

The data for this study were collected using pre-test and post-test achievement tests administered to the students. The tests for the experimental and control groups were kept separate and were used to address the research questions and test the hypotheses guiding the study. To answer the research questions, mean and standard deviation were used. For hypothesis testing, an independent t-test was employed at an alpha level of 0.05. The independent t-test was selected to compare the

achievement scores of the experimental and control groups, in order to determine whether there was a statistically significant difference between the two groups.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the difference in academic achievement between students taught probability using dice games and those taught without using dice games?

Table 1: Mean achievement scores and standard deviations of students taught probability using dice games and those taught without dice games.

Group	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean gain
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Experimental	50	11.14	1.87	16.62	1.79	5.48
Control	50	10.26	1.32	14.22	1.47	3.96

The result in Table 1 indicates that students taught with dice games performed better than those taught without dice games. This is evident from the mean gain of 5.48 for the experimental group, which is higher than the 3.96 mean gain for the control group.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in academic achievement between students taught probability using dice games and those taught without dice games.

Table 2: Summary of t-test Analysis on the mean achievement scores of students taught probability using dice games and those without dice games

Group	N	Mean	SD	df	t	Sig(2tailed)	Decision
Experimental	50	16.62	1.79	98	7.31	.00	S
Control	50	14.22	1.47				

*significant at $p < .05$

Table 2 shows that $t(98) = 7.31$ is significant at $p = .00$, which is also significant at the .05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected, indicating that there is a significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught probability with dice games and those taught without dice games.

Research Question 2: What is the difference in academic achievement of male and female students in the concept of probability using dice games?

performed better than their female counterparts. Moreover, a significant difference in achievement was found between male and female students taught with dice games, indicating that dice games had a more positive effect on male students' performance. This finding is consistent with Onoh (2015), who observed that males generally achieved higher than females in mathematics. It also supports the findings of Gbodi and Laleye (2010), who reported significant differences in the academic performance of male and female students, with males outperforming females.

Conclusion

This study investigated the impact of dice games on students' academic achievement in the concept of probability in mathematics. The results of the analysis revealed that the use of dice games was significantly more effective than the conventional method of teaching mathematics. Additionally, the findings showed a notable disparity in academic achievement between male and female students, with male students outperforming their female counterparts. Overall, the study demonstrated that incorporating dice games into mathematics instruction is an effective approach to enhancing students' academic performance in the subject.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Secondary school mathematics teachers should be encouraged to incorporate dice games as part of their teaching strategies, especially when teaching complex concepts like probability. This approach has been shown to improve students' academic achievement and can make learning more engaging and interactive.
2. Since the study found that male students performed better than female students when taught with dice games, it is recommended that educators consider gender-sensitive teaching methods. Teachers should strive to create an inclusive learning environment that caters to the learning needs of both male and female students.
3. Mathematics teachers should receive professional development training on the effective use of educational games, such as dice games, in the classroom. This will ensure they are well-equipped with innovative teaching strategies that can enhance students' understanding of mathematical concepts.
4. The government, in collaboration with curriculum developers and mathematics educators, should review the existing mathematics curriculum and incorporate elements of the game-based approach. This integration would ensure that the benefits of game-based learning are systematically embedded in the educational framework.

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